

Thermodynamics of Acid Dissociation Equilibria of Some *N*-Substituted Anilinium Ions in Formamide

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The acid dissociation constants of *N*-substituted anilinium ions have been determined accurately in formamide over the temperature range 10-50° (283.15-323.15 K) from the measurement of the e.m.f. of the cells,

The dissociation constants at 25° (298.15 K) have been checked by determining the same with the help of the cells,

Thermodynamical changes, ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° for the dissociation processes have been evaluated. The results show that the dissociation constants of these conjugate acids are in general lower (pK_a 's higher) in formamide than their corresponding values in water.

In our recent communications^{1,2}, we reported the acid dissociation constants of anilinium, nitroanilinium and bromoanilinium ions in formamide, a solvent of high dielectric constant (109.5) over the temperature range 10-50° (283.15-323.15 K) and related thermodynamical quantities as determined from e.m.f. measurements using cells of the type (A).

where B represents the base. It was also reported that the values of dissociation constants at 25° (298.15 K) as determined from the cells of the type (A) agree well with those obtained from e.m.f. measurements of cells of the type (B).

The acid dissociation constants of *N*-methyl, *N*-ethyl, and *N,N*-dimethylanilinium ions in formamide, at several temperatures following the same procedure and using cells of the same types, are reported in this paper. This forms a part of the general programme in this laboratory to study different types of ionic equilibria in formamide, a solvent having a dielectric constant higher than that of water and a much wider liquid range.

Experimental

The aniline bases studied were all good quality products and were purified further by vacuum distillation. The hydrochlorides of the bases were prepared and purified by the standard procedures. The purity of the bases was checked by boiling point measurements and that of the hydrochlorides by titration. All the chemicals were stored in desiccators over Drierite until required. The bases and their hydrochlorides were handled in dry nitrogen atmosphere using a dry-box, the weighing of the compounds was performed using a closed weighing

bottle which had been loaded in the dry-box. Formamide (L.R., S.D.'s) was purified as described³ earlier.

The preparation of the solutions for e.m.f. measurements, filling and setting up of cells (A) and (B), thermostating of the solutions and measurements of e.m.f. were all similar to those described earlier^{1,4}.

All measurements were reduced to 760 mm pressure. The vapour pressure of formamide was estimated to be less than 10 mm at temperatures below 60° (333.15 K) from data available in the literature. In most cases the correction for barometric pressure was found to be negligible.

Results and Discussion

As described in the earlier communication¹, the acid dissociation constant, K_a , of the conjugate acid is related to the e.m.f., E , of cells (A) and (B) through equation (1).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{F(E - E^\circ)}{2.303 RT} + \log \frac{m(\text{BH}^+)m(\text{Cl}^-)}{m(\text{B})} \\ = -\log K_a - \log \frac{\gamma(\text{BH}^+) \gamma(\text{Cl}^-)}{\gamma(\text{B})} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where E° is the standard e.m.f. of the cell, m and γ are, respectively, molalities and activity coefficients of the species shown in parentheses. Since $m(\text{Cl}^-) = m_2$, $m(\text{BH}^+) = m_2 - m(\text{H}^+)$, and $m(\text{B}) = m_1 + m(\text{H}^+)$, the second term of the left hand side of equation (1) was calculated from the experimental data when $m(\text{H}^+)$ was negligible compared to m_1 and m_2 as this becomes equal to $\log m_2^2/m_1$. The left hand side of equation (1), which may be represented by $-\log K'_a$, will vary with the ionic strength of the medium and will yield $-\log K_a$ when

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF $-\log K_a$ OF *N*-METHYLANILINIUM ION (*N*-MeAnH⁺) IN FORMAMIDE AT 25° (298.15 K)

$10^3 m_1$ mol kg ⁻¹	$10^3 m_s = 10^3 \mu$ mol kg ⁻¹	$\frac{E}{V}$	$\frac{F(E - E^0)}{2.303 RT}$	$-\log \frac{m_2}{m_1}$	$-\log K_a'$	$-\log K_a$
From study of cell (A)						
0.665	0.412	0.6585	7.7777	2.5930	5.1847	
0.932	0.680	0.6445	7.5410	2.8044	5.2866	
1.228	0.764	0.6415	7.4903	2.8290	5.1673	5.26
1.043	0.918	0.6228	7.1742	2.0926	5.0816	± 0.04
1.296	1.052	0.6244	7.2013	2.0686	5.1327	
1.418	1.262	0.6162	7.0627	1.9496	5.1131	
From study of cell (B)						
0.925	0.616	-0.0615	7.6732	2.3870	5.2862	
0.898	0.702	-0.0700	7.5295	2.2606	5.2689	
1.236	0.852	-0.0738	7.4653	2.2311	5.2342	
1.076	1.005	-0.0935	7.1323	2.0275	5.1048	5.33
1.480	1.226	-0.0878	7.2287	1.9933	5.2354	± 0.06
1.596	1.318	-0.0915	7.1661	1.9632	5.2029	

 TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF $-\log K_a$ OF *N*-ETHYLANILINIUM ION (*N*-EtAnH⁺) IN FORMAMIDE AT 25° (298.15 K)

$10^3 m_1$ mol kg ⁻¹	$10^3 m_s = 10^3 \mu$ mol kg ⁻¹	$\frac{E}{V}$	$\frac{F(E - E^0)}{2.303 RT}$	$-\log \frac{m_2}{m_1}$	$-\log K_a'$	$-\log K_a$
From study of cell (A)						
0.708	0.328	0.6815	8.1665	2.8183	5.3482	
0.926	0.487	0.6771	8.0921	2.6556	5.4065	
1.088	0.516	0.6694	7.9620	2.6118	5.3507	5.47
1.385	0.743	0.6596	7.6949	2.8995	5.2954	± 0.03
1.640	0.908	0.6410	7.4819	2.2987	5.1832	
1.832	1.075	0.6376	7.4244	2.3001	5.2243	
From study of cell (B)						
0.813	0.406	-0.0348	8.1246	2.6930	5.4316	
1.165	0.613	-0.0506	7.8575	2.4914	5.3661	
1.408	0.732	-0.0575	7.7408	2.4196	5.3212	5.57
1.551	0.844	-0.0683	7.5583	2.3979	5.2204	± 0.03
1.793	0.917	-0.0670	7.5803	2.3288	5.2515	
2.066	1.139	-0.0779	7.8960	2.2021	5.1939	

 TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF $-\log K_a$ OF *N,N*-DIMETHYLANILINIUM ION (*N,N*-Me₂AnH⁺) IN FORMAMIDE AT 25° (298.15 K)

$10^3 m_1$ mol kg ⁻¹	$10^3 m_s = 10^3 \mu$ mol kg ⁻¹	$\frac{E}{V}$	$\frac{F(E - E^0)}{2.303 RT}$	$-\log \frac{m_2}{m_1}$	$-\log K_a'$	$-\log K_a$
From study of cell (A)						
0.790	0.234	0.6985	8.4539	3.1692	5.2947	
1.136	0.408	0.6704	7.9789	2.8341	5.1448	
1.034	0.562	0.6556	7.7287	2.5856	5.1931	5.40
1.448	0.705	0.6425	7.5072	2.4644	5.0428	± 0.04
1.780	0.768	0.6402	7.4684	2.4797	4.9887	
1.915	0.835	0.6388	7.4447	2.4388	5.0059	
From study of cell (B)						
0.986	0.325	-0.0226	8.3308	2.9701	5.3607	
0.872	0.416	-0.0424	7.9961	2.7023	5.2938	
1.558	0.604	-0.0535	7.8085	2.6305	5.1780	
1.392	0.685	-0.0705	7.5211	2.4723	5.0488	5.53
1.608	0.772	-0.0718	7.4991	2.4311	5.0680	± 0.04
1.990	0.926	-0.0776	7.4011	2.3657	5.0354	

extrapolated to zero ionic strength, the ionic strength of the solution, μ , being given by m_s .

The pK_a values obtained by this procedure over the temperature range 10-50° (283.15-323.15 K) are

shown in Table 4 alongwith the standard deviations calculated by the method of least squares. Typical e.m.f. readings of cells (A) and (B) and other data needed for the computation of $-\log K_a$ at 25° (298.15 K) are shown in Tables 1-3.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON $-\log K_a$ FROM STUDY OF CELL (A) IN FORMAMIDE

Temp. °C	$-\log K_a$		
	<i>N</i> -MeAnH ⁺	<i>N</i> -EtAnH ⁺	<i>N,N</i> -Me ₂ AnH ⁺
10	5.38 ± 0.06	5.61 ± 0.02	5.65 ± 0.06
15	5.28 ± 0.04	5.68 ± 0.03	5.48 ± 0.05
20	5.26 ± 0.05	5.55 ± 0.02	5.50 ± 0.05
25	5.26 ± 0.04 (5.33 ± 0.06)*	5.47 ± 0.03 (5.57 ± 0.03)*	5.40 ± 0.04 (5.53 ± 0.04)*
30	5.14 ± 0.03	5.33 ± 0.01	5.28 ± 0.05
35	4.94 ± 0.03	5.26 ± 0.03	5.20 ± 0.07
40	5.05 ± 0.03	5.27 ± 0.02	5.19 ± 0.09
45	4.96 ± 0.03	5.18 ± 0.02	5.00 ± 0.05
50	4.88 ± 0.05	5.15 ± 0.03	5.09 ± 0.04

* Values in parentheses from study of cell (B).

A comparison of the present pK_a data with the corresponding values in water is not possible because of the lack of relevant data in water at all temperatures. However, available data at 25° (298.15 K) (Table 5) show that pK_a values are higher in formamide than in water which is in complete agreement with our previous observations^{1,2} and with the general behaviour of the conjugate acids of bases and of weak acids in solvents of this class⁴⁻⁸. The pK_a values obtained for these conjugate acids at 25° (298.15 K) with cell (B) are slightly higher than those obtained with cell (A) (Table 4). Taking the limitations of the quinhydrone electrode in media containing amines into consideration, this agreement is quite satisfactory and confirms our earlier suggestion^{1,2} that quinhydrone electrode behaves more satisfactorily in formamide than in water, even in the presence of amines.

A comparison of the pK_a values of these conjugate acids at 25° (298.15 K) in different solvents (Table 5) shows that in general, the pK_a values are not linearly related to $1/D$ (where D is the dielectric constant of the medium) as suggested by Born equation, although they seem to depend, to a large extent, on the dielectric constant of the medium. The fact that the pK_a values of these conjugate acids are higher in formamide than in water even though the latter has a lower dielectric constant, may be due to the lower basicity of formamide compared to that of water as already suggested⁹.

TABLE 5— pK_a VALUES OF ANILINIUM IONS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AT 25° (298.15 K)

Ion	Water ^b D=78.54	Formamide ^a D=109.5	Nitromethane ^c D=35.9	Acetic acid ^d D=6.2
<i>N</i> -MeAnH ⁺	4.85	5.26	—	2.67
<i>N</i> -EtAnH ⁺	5.11	5.47	—	2.83
<i>N,N</i> -Me ₂ AnH ⁺	5.06	5.40	11.04	2.86
AnH ⁺	4.58	5.10 ^e	9.07	—

^a Present work, ^b Ref. 10, ^c Ref. 11, ^d Ref. 12, ^e Ref. 1.

As expected, the increase of temperature has a general effect of lowering the pK_a values of these conjugate acids (Table 4). However, in agreement with the earlier studies, irregularities are noticed for which there is no ready explanation. As has been

suggested earlier^{1,2}, these might be due to minute structural changes occurring in the hydrogen bonded solvent with the change of temperature.

The thermodynamic properties, ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° have been evaluated as described earlier¹ on the assumption that ΔH° does not change appreciably over the temperature range used. The plots of $\log K_a$ vs $1/T$ are linear in all the cases, thereby implying that the assumption is reasonable. The results are shown in Table 6 along with those for anilinium ion, but a comparison with the results in aqueous medium is not possible due to the lack of relevant data in the literature.

TABLE 6—STANDARD THERMODYNAMIC VALUES FOR DISSOCIATION PROCESS $BH^+ \rightleftharpoons B + H^+$ IN FORMAMIDE AT 25° (298.15 K)

Base (B)	ΔG° kJ mole ⁻¹	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
<i>N</i> -Methylaniline	30.03	21.41	-28.91
<i>N</i> -Ethylaniline	31.23	23.88	-24.65
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylaniline	30.83	26.18	-15.60
Aniline	29.11*	27.28*	-6.14*

* Ref. 1.

These results show that ΔG° values of the dissociation processes for anilinium and *N*-substituted anilinium ions in formamide appear in the order,

which is similar to that found in aqueous medium on the basis of pK_a data shown in column 1 of Table 5. It is further found that in formamide medium ΔH° values appear in the order,

The relative orders of ΔH° between *N*-MeAnH⁺ and *N*-EtAnH⁺ and between *N*-MeAnH⁺ and *N,N*-Me₂AnH⁺ are quite expected from the standpoint of the inductive effects of the groups attached to the nitrogen atom. As is well known, the ethyl group will exert a larger inductive effect than the methyl group and the combined inductive effect of two methyl groups will be obviously greater than that of a single methyl group. However, when these ΔH° values for *N*-substituted anilinium ions are compared with that for the anilinium ion, the foregoing rule seems to breakdown completely. The relative acidity of these anilinium ions, therefore, can not be explained on the basis of the inductive effects of the groups attached to the nitrogen atom as is commonly done. The reason for their apparent order lies elsewhere as can be seen from the ΔS° values for the dissociation processes. These values appear in the order,

which is the same as that for the ΔH° values also. But when these two sets of values are combined through the relation, $\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$, the ΔG° values appear in a different order as discussed above.

Thus, in reality, ΔG° values of these anilinium ions are much more complicated functions of substrate and solvent properties as reflected through their corresponding ΔH° and ΔS° values and any effort to correlate these with either substrate or solvent properties alone would be generally futile.

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